

Workflow for CLEM image correlation with BigWarp (Fiji)

Start Fiji and load the images to correlate. In this example it is an overlay of two single images. However, this program works also very good to correlate two 3D stacks of images!

Start “BigWarp”

Chose LM image as moving image and TEM image as target image, then press OK.

3 windows appear: Moving and target image and the landmark list.

Make the windows bigger.
Zoom and navigate with
the mouse wheel. Press
"space bar" to switch to
landmark mode.

Left click to corresponding structures on both images (in landmark mode). The pair will appear as one entry in the landmark list.

Add a second point.

Add a third point.

Add a fourth point.

After adding four point pairs one can press “T” (transform). Now the moving image will be transformed. If one presses “Q” both images will get aligned to a similar view.

Hotkey "F" on the active image switches on the fused view. If correlation is still not good, add more point pairs. The updating will always be done live after the second point is added.

Once done, export the moving image as a separate file.

Just press OK here.
The export will take some
time, as now the transform
is applied and the image is
rescaled to the size of the
target image.

The resulting file is opened in Fiji and needs to be saved manually. It has the same dimensions as the original target image and can be used for further overlays or analyses.

T	Toggle between warped view and raw view or moving image.
^ Ctrl + O	Open landmarks from saved file.
^ Ctrl + S	Save current landmarks to a file.
_ Space	Toggle <i>Landmark mode</i>
<Landmark mode>+ Left Click	Clicking while in landmark mode adds a landmark point or selects an existing landmark.
<Landmark mode>+ Left Drag	Clicking an existing point and dragging changes its position.
V	Toggle point visibility in the viewer.
N	Toggle point name visibility in the viewer.
Q	Align the non-active viewer with the active viewer.
W	Align the active viewer with the non-active viewer.
R	Resets the active viewer.
Left Drag	Rotate (pan and tilt) around the point where the mouse was clicked.
Right Drag or Middle Drag	Translate in the XY-plane.
Mouse Wheel	Move along the z-axis.
Command + Mouse Wheel or Shift + ^ Ctrl + Mouse Wheel	Zoom in and out.

Useful hotkeys in BigWarp:

<https://imagej.net/plugins/bigwarp>